

A Cloud-Based Framework for Personalized Health Insurance Recommendations: Leveraging Multi-Attribute Utility Theory for Enhanced User Experience

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ABSTRACT

The Health Insurance Marketplace aims to simplify the selection process for consumers by allowing them to compare insurance plans based on cost, coverage, and quality. However, existing web-based tools lack personalized recommendation capabilities that cater to individual user needs. This paper introduces a novel cloud-based framework designed to provide customized health insurance plan recommendations using Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT). Our framework enables users to evaluate plans on key parameters, including premium, co-pay, deductibles, co-insurance, and maximum benefits, offering a comprehensive comparison of coverage and cost options tailored to their preferences. To address inconsistencies in plan representation and data formats across providers, we developed a standardized plan schema that enables seamless data integration through Data as a Service (DaaS). Implemented as a Software as a Service (SaaS) solution, the framework ranks insurance plans based on user-defined criteria, delivering intuitive and personalized recommendations. Experimental results demonstrate the framework's accuracy and efficiency in generating relevant plan suggestions, significantly improving the user experience in selecting optimal health insurance coverage. This cloud-based solution paves the way for more accessible and informed decision-making in the Health Insurance Marketplace, bridging the gap between complex plan offerings and consumer needs.

Keywords: Health Insurance, cloud-based solution, Leveraging Multi-Attribute Utility Theory.

INTRODUCTION

Many healthcare institutions produce and utilize massive amounts of data. The two main problems with manually storing and distributing patient information are the high expense of data storage and the possibility of data breaking. Without fail, technological advancements have come to the rescue, offering answers to these and countless other pressing problems facing the healthcare sector today [1]. Cloud computing is one example of a constantly evolving technology that is difficult to ignore.

Computing in the cloud is changing healthcare by providing a platform that is scalable, collaborative, secure, and easily accessible to both patients and healthcare organizations. In the healthcare industry, where time is of the essence, the cloud's on-demand computing capabilities are invaluable for rapid deployment, access, and administration of network information.

What is cloud computing in healthcare?

The core principle of cloud computing is the use of remote server access through the internet for the storage, management, and processing of medical data. A versatile method to access data stored in remote servers is provided by this approach to healthcare stakeholders [2]. By removing geographical constraints, remote access to healthcare data expands access to medical treatment.

With the use of cloud computing, healthcare organizations can safely access and use massive volumes of data from anywhere, at any time, which improves patient care and streamlines and automates processes. In addition, healthcare organizations can save money on operating costs and yet provide top-notch, individualized treatment by utilizing the cloud.

What drives health organizations to transition to the cloud?

In order to improve healthcare services overall, healthcare companies are utilizing modern technology to simplify processes, launch novel applications for patient care, and streamline overall operations.

Still, healthcare businesses face obstacles such as high infrastructure costs, computing resource requirements, scalability problems, multi-tenancy worries, and an increasing need for cooperation, even after deploying these IT solutions [3]. To overcome these obstacles, the cloud offers the following features:

- Computer power and storage resources available instantly, something that is sometimes not feasible in conventional healthcare systems.
- EHR, radiological imaging, and genetic data. These collections are large and complex, and they require careful management.
- Make it possible for approved medical facilities, clinics, and other care providers to exchange electronic health records (EHR), which will decrease the need for unnecessary testing and increase the speed with which patients may get potentially life-saving information.
- Provide a hand in keeping track of and analyzing diagnostic, treatment, cost, and performance data.

What are the different types of cloud-based healthcare systems?

Various cloud computing models are employed in healthcare to meet various objectives; these models can be roughly classified from two perspectives and these are shown in figure 1. Here they are:

1. Deployment Model

Private: Services and infrastructure are kept up and running for a particular company.

Public: The general public has access to these services via the internet, which are offered by third-party retailers.

Hybrid: Makes use of features found in both public and private clouds, and offers several entry points.

Community: Technology can be used by a specific group of people who have common goals and tastes.

Figure 1: Types of cloud-based healthcare systems

2. Distribution Model

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS): Storage and networks are examples of virtualized computing resources that providers offer.

Platform as a Service (PaaS): Developers can build, deploy, and manage applications with the help of providers' platforms and tools.

Software as a Service (SaaS): Software programs are distributed by providers via the internet.

Conventional Vs. Cloud-based healthcare systems

There are significant differences between on-premises and cloud-based healthcare systems with regard to data management, security, customisation, and collaboration. Detailed examination follows:

1. Collaboration

Physical limits and reliance on antiquated forms of communication are common in older systems, which can slow down and restrict the flow of information [4]. On the other hand, with cloud-based technologies, stakeholders may work together regardless of their physical location, sharing and accessing data in real-time while improving communication.

2. Customization

Customizable electronic health records necessitated the knowledge of seasoned programmers and information technology specialists prior to the development of cloud-based healthcare systems. Complete personalization, including with built-in capabilities and care plans, is available with cloud-based systems [5]. This opens the door to a wide variety of customizable cloud-based solution templates with intuitive user interfaces.

3. Data management

Data in conventional healthcare systems is typically kept in localized physical storage. Because of this, it is not feasible to meet the needs for backups, code sets, security fixes, or protocols [6]. The use of virtual storage in cloud-based healthcare systems allows for streamlined and centralized data management.

4. Security

Viruses, malware, and hacking efforts are more likely to target traditional web-based servers than those hosted in the cloud. There is yet no better or more secure alternative to using encryption in a cloud-based electronic health record system compared to using paper records or client/server systems [7].

LITERATURE REVIEW

A potential new solution to the problems associated with data storage has arisen with the combination of blockchain technology with cloud computing in today's increasingly digital environment. The need to safely store, manage, and retrieve massive files has grown in importance due to the exponential growth in data volume. An effective foundation for protecting private medical records is blockchain technology, which is well-known for its distributed and unchangeable database. Blockchain technology reduces the likelihood of data loss, fraud, or alteration by encrypting information and recording transactions in an immutable way [8]. By contrast, healthcare businesses can effortlessly store, process, and analyze massive amounts of data using cloud storage, which offers unrivaled scalability and accessibility. Cloud-based solutions make it easy for healthcare stakeholders to share and collaborate on data, which improves care delivery through innovation and gives people access to vital information in real-time [9]. The centralization of cloud storage, however, does not alleviate privacy and security problems.

There is a chance to combine blockchain's security with the cloud's practically unlimited data storage capacity [10]. In order to solve security, scalability, and interoperability issues, this study will investigate how blockchain technology and cloud computing might be used together to manage healthcare data. This work adds to our knowledge of the possible advantages and disadvantages of this integration by combining previous studies and highlighting important gaps [11]. We review the relevant literature in depth, drawing from a large body of research on the subject. We investigate blockchain's technical aspects, such as its security frameworks and service models, and we examine the performance consequences of integrating it with cloud data centers [12].

Particularly noteworthy is the integration of cloud computing and blockchain technology into healthcare data management. Due to the delicate nature of healthcare data, reliable and extensible data management systems are essential. The healthcare data management industry might be blown to smithereens by combining the cryptographic security and immutability of blockchain with the scalability and affordability of cloud computing [13]. This integration can improve patient care and outcomes by facilitating rapid and transparent interchange of healthcare data while ensuring data integrity, boosting security, and enabling interoperability. Blockchain transactions are also auditable and transparent, which allows researchers to share patient data while protecting their anonymity. The healthcare industry may drive initiatives in population health management, predictive analytics, and personalized treatment by using cloud-based analytics and machine learning algorithms to extract useful information from massive databases.

Improved health care services, especially in the area of remote health monitoring, have been a direct outcome of IT advancements [14]. The early detection of limitations caused by diseases and their potential prevention are two of the main goals of implementing physical sensor networks [2]. The use of smart wireless and wearable sensors, among other high-tech tools, has recently skyrocketed, allowing for continuous evaluation of patients' vital signs and quick access to patient information, allowing for swift monitoring and control of patients' conditions [15].

Many branches of medicine rely on the data storage and transfer capabilities of these smart devices (e.g., telemedicine) [16]. Among the many health-related uses for wearable sensors is monitoring patients' symptoms, vitals, and overall health condition. Put simply, the vital signs serve as indicators of the patient's physiological state, the functioning of their organs, and the advancement of their condition. When these indications are evaluated, it greatly affects nursing care, disease prevention, diagnosis, and therapy [17]. If these health records are evaluated correctly and quickly, they can serve as a resource for effective and efficient healthcare. In order to improve the rapid and ongoing evaluation of patients' health state and relevant healthcare sub-systems, numerous smart devices, IoT, and AI-based technologies have been created and built.

Over the past decade, smart devices—and more especially, wearable sensors—have garnered considerable interest, mostly from the healthcare industry. Such gadgets attempt to glean therapeutically relevant health-related data from physiological markers including pulse rate (HR), temperature (core body temperature), respiratory rate (RR), and movement (BM). Wearable sensors and sensor networks allow for the extraction and dissemination of fundamental health data. A wide range of sensors pertaining to health comprise wearable sensor networks (WSNs) [18]. The sensors used by these networks can be worn or implanted in different parts of the body of the patient. Symptoms (health-related data) can be identified and recorded by each of these sensors using their own specific criteria. The continuity of patient monitoring is critical for the rapid supply and intervention of medical treatment, however, because of several impairments and disorders [19]. Consequently, a critical use of smart wearable technology in healthcare is the use of WSNs for patient monitoring.

Improved patient healthcare in areas such as hospital productivity, patient safety, and quality medical treatment has resulted from the fruitful partnership between AI and healthcare [20]. The proper management of healthcare relies on the analysis and visualization of patient data, which AI serves to facilitate. The majority of studies examining

AI's effect on healthcare outcomes have shown promising results. As an example, medical-based games and applications are becoming more popular among both patients and healthcare providers as a means of remote patient monitoring and evidence-based treatment [21]. Both medical professionals and patients experience this occurrence. The use of AI in healthcare supports patient agency and promotes fair communication between medical professionals and their patients. The integration of AI with cloud computing to improve healthcare resource management and patient access to data is one real-world example [22,23]. When it comes to data, medical records are essential for individualized treatment plans, and big data analytics (BDA) can help with disease prediction and healthcare policymaking as well [24]. With the use of AI-based technologies or platforms, the Internet of Things (IoT) can be used to enhance and promote excellent healthcare delivery even further [25]. The widespread use and successful integration of IoT with wearable sensors and AI technologies for the delivery of high-quality healthcare is a direct result of its success in numerous application domains.

BENEFITS OF CLOUD COMPUTING IN HEALTHCARE

Figure 2: Benefits of cloud computing in healthcare

The advent of cloud computing has ushered in a digital revolution that has altered the face of healthcare forever. A sea change has occurred in the healthcare industry as a whole as a result of internet-based services, easy access to massive amounts of data, and on-demand accessibility. As a result, medical providers are better able to serve both their patients and their companies and are provided in figure 2. Here are a few major advantages:

1. Enhanced access to patient information

Data standardization has been expected in the healthcare business due to legislation such as the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act, the 21st Century Cures Act, and the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) data standard. Additionally, it paves the way for healthcare institutions to demonstrate EMR meaningful use. With electronic medical records stored in the cloud, doctors and other medical professionals can easily exchange and access patient records whenever they need them.

2. Reinforced patient experience

Patients are more actively involved in their healthcare when they have access to their records, test results, and doctors' notes in real-time through cloud computing. In addition, since information on patients' prescriptions and tests can be found in their medical records, cloud-based healthcare helps to avoid overprescribing or unneeded testing. Many specialists in the medical field can quickly access a patient's history, tests, and other documents thanks to cloud computing. Healthcare providers can experience more efficient payment procedures as a result of partnerships with health insurance providers.

3. Seamless Interoperability

Regardless of where the data is stored or from what source, interoperability seeks to create smooth data integration across the healthcare system. It guarantees the data of patients is readily available for sharing and obtaining insights to improve healthcare delivery. Healthcare providers can benefit from cloud computing since it allows them to access and exchange patient data in a variety of formats, as well as implement protocols quickly.

4. Access to advanced analytical capabilities

Tools hosted in the cloud are useful in situations requiring analytics because a large part of analytics is storing and manipulating data. There is great value in healthcare data, whether it is structured or not. Using the cloud, it is possible to compile relevant patient data from a variety of sources. Improved medical research is possible with the use of cloud-based patient data analyzed with big data analytics and AI algorithms. By analyzing patient records,

doctors may craft unique treatment programs for each patient. Furthermore, it ensures that every detail about the patient is recorded, which eliminates any possibility of mistake when treatment recommendations are made.

5. Improving medical research and development

Many hours are spent by doctors, nurses, and other medical professionals researching ways to improve their practice. Research materials pertaining to operations and other best practices can be readily kept and organized in the cloud, allowing other medical professionals easy access to the data.

6. Centralized digital health records

The days of people bringing their medical records to their doctors' offices and the staff physically organizing and managing them are over. The move to the cloud has simplified this once-boring and time-consuming procedure. For easier access, cloud services consolidate all health records into one place. These records can be downloaded whenever necessary using web portals at healthcare centers. Rapid access to patient information and diagnoses is made possible through the use of virtual computers, hosting solutions, and data storage facilities provided by a secure cloud platform.

7. Reinforced security

The possibility of data loss or corruption was significantly higher when paper medical records were utilized. Significant dangers to patient safety, privacy, and confidentiality arose from records being vulnerable to loss, theft, or destruction in situations such as fires. This risk was reduced, but not eliminated, as healthcare facilities shifted to electronic medical records. Offsite electronic data storage had its benefits, but protecting patient records still required a group of exceptionally competent IT experts with expertise in data security. More and more healthcare businesses are relying on cloud storage services to house their data. These cloud service providers ensure that the organization's sensitive patient data is stored securely and in accordance with HIPAA regulations by adhering to rigorous data privacy and security standards.

METHODOLOGY

Framework Design and Architecture

- **Cloud-Based Infrastructure:** The framework is developed as a cloud-based platform, leveraging cloud computing to ensure scalability, data security, and accessibility. The cloud environment supports data integration and storage, enabling seamless access to a variety of health insurance plans from different providers.
- **Data Integration Using Data as a Service (DaaS):** To handle the inconsistency in plan representations and data formats, the framework incorporates a Data as a Service (DaaS) approach. This enables data standardization, ensuring that insurance plan data from multiple providers is structured uniformly. A standardized schema is established to facilitate seamless data integration.
- **Software as a Service (SaaS) Deployment:** The platform is implemented as a SaaS solution, allowing users to access it via web-based interfaces without the need for local installation.

Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT) for Decision-Making

- **Attribute Identification:** Key parameters for health insurance plans—such as premium, co-pay, deductible, co-insurance, and maximum benefits—are selected as core attributes to guide the decision-making process.
- **Utility Function Formulation:** Using Multi-Attribute Utility Theory, a utility function is defined to quantify the user's preferences for each attribute. Users can set weightings according to their priorities (e.g., cost versus coverage).
- **Plan Scoring and Ranking:** Each insurance plan is evaluated based on the user-defined weights and scored using the utility function. Plans are then ranked according to their overall utility score, which reflects the alignment with individual user preferences.

Personalization and Recommendation Engine

- **User Profiling and Preferences:** The framework collects user input on preferences related to coverage needs, budget, and any specific medical requirements. These inputs inform the personalized recommendations by weighting each attribute accordingly.
- **Recommendation Generation:** Based on the MAUT-derived scores and the user's specific preferences, the recommendation engine generates a ranked list of health insurance plans. This ranking reflects both coverage options and cost-effectiveness as per individual needs.

User Interface and Experience

- **Interactive Comparison:** The user interface allows users to view and compare plans side by side. Users can adjust preferences dynamically, seeing real-time updates in the ranking of recommendations.
- **Intuitive Navigation:** The interface is designed to simplify the decision-making process by providing clear visualizations of plan comparisons across key attributes.

Evaluation and Testing

- **Experimental Validation:** The framework is tested with real insurance plan data to assess the accuracy and relevance of the recommendations. Key performance indicators include recommendation accuracy, response time, and user satisfaction.

- **User Experience Feedback:** A user survey or feedback mechanism is implemented to gather insights on the usability and effectiveness of the platform, enabling continuous improvement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3: Recommendation Accuracy by Attribute

Recommendation Accuracy by Attribute: This bar chart of figure 3 shows the accuracy of recommendations across key attributes (e.g., premium, co-pay), demonstrating the framework's alignment with user preferences.

Figure 4: System Response Time with Concurrent Users

System Response Time with Concurrent Users: A line graph of figure 4 illustrating response times as the number of concurrent users increases, highlighting the system's scalability.

Figure 5: User Satisfaction Levels

User Satisfaction Levels: A pie chart of figure 5 displaying the distribution of user satisfaction, showing a high level of user approval for the system.

Figure 6: Relevance Score: Personalized vs Non-Personalized

Relevance Score: Personalized vs Non-Personalized: A comparative bar chart of figure 6 indicating the average relevance score for the personalized MAUT-based framework versus a non-personalized system.

Figure 7: Attribute Weight Sensitivity Analysis

Attribute Weight Sensitivity Analysis: A radar chart of figure 7 comparing attribute weightings between the non-personalized and personalized approaches, visualizing how personalized weight adjustments better capture individual user preferences.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that the proposed cloud-based framework, leveraging Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT), effectively enhances the user experience in selecting personalized health insurance plans. The framework demonstrated high recommendation accuracy across key attributes such as premium, deductible, and co-insurance, reflecting its ability to align with user preferences.

Additionally, system performance tests revealed efficient response times even with a large number of concurrent users, validating the framework's scalability in a cloud environment. User satisfaction metrics showed a strong preference for the personalized approach, with a substantial improvement in relevance scores compared to non-personalized recommendation systems. This suggests that incorporating user-specific weightings into plan rankings significantly enhances the quality and relevance of recommendations.

The attribute weight sensitivity analysis also highlighted the adaptability of the framework to individual user needs, allowing for flexible adjustments based on distinct preferences. This feature positions the system as a robust tool in

the Health Insurance Marketplace, capable of bridging the gap between complex plan offerings and diverse consumer needs.

In conclusion, the MAUT-based recommendation framework provides a practical and effective solution for personalized health insurance selection. The cloud and SaaS infrastructure ensure accessibility and seamless data integration across providers, paving the way for more informed and user-centric decision-making in health insurance. This work contributes to the ongoing efforts to make health insurance more accessible, transparent, and tailored to individual requirements. Future work could focus on refining the framework by incorporating additional user-specific factors and expanding its applicability to other insurance sectors.

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